

BUILT 07

Mobility outside

How to facilitate increased mobility of older adults in outdoor environments

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Warsaw University
of Technology

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BUILT

MODULE 7

Mobility outside

In this module you will learn how to facilitate increased mobility of older adults in outdoor environments.

Mobility

Optimal mobility is defined as being able to safely and reliably go

- where you want to go,
- when you want to go ,
- in a way you want to get there.

Optimal mobility is one of the key components of healthy ageing.

Mobility is a broad issue which refers to movement from basic ambulation, walking for leisure and the completion of daily tasks, using various forms of public transport to exercising. This module will help you to understand why mobility is often closely related to mental health and which issues are important in facilitating older adults when going outside. Moreover, you will learn what principles should be taken into consideration when creating a safe route for older adults.

What will you learn in this module

- 1 What is the influence of mobility on mental health of older adults
- 2 What are the main barriers for older adults in terms of mobility outside
- 3 What are the main needs of older adults when going outside
- 4 Which places are important for older adults in their neighbourhood
- 5 Which items are important when going outside
- 6 Mobility and dementia
- 7 How to create a safe route

Chapters in this module

1

Mobility and mental health

2

Main barriers

3

Main needs

4

Important places

5

Necessary items

6

Mobility and dementia

7

Safe routes

BUILT

MODULE 7

CHAPTER 1

Mobility and mental health

This chapter will provide information and evidence of some common mental health benefits connected to the active social lives of older adults.

Mobility and mental health

Mental well-being is a crucial part of healthy ageing alongside physical health. There are some key mental health risks that are related to reduced mobility such as social isolation, loneliness, and lower levels of contact with friends and family. These issues have a profound negative effect on mental well-being.

What will you learn in this chapter

- 1 What is scientific evidence on negative aspects of loneliness
- 2 What are the mental health benefits of older adults socialisation
- 3 What are other benefits of older adults socialisation
- 4 How to keep social contacts in older age

Mobility and mental health

No matter what age a person is, social contacts are important and give a person a sense of belonging and acceptance. Obviously, older adults are no different; they need contact with other people just as much as a children, teenagers, and adults of all ages. As people, we need social contacts to thrive and enjoy fulfilling lives.

Social contacts become more significant as we get older. According to a research study performed by Harvard University School of Public Health, older people who lead an intense social life are happier, healthier and more likely to live longer, than older people who do not have an active social life. There is a lot of scientific evidence on negative aspects of loneliness especially in older age. Authors of a study from Brigham Young University found out that the

impact of social isolation on mortality is equivalent to smoking 15 cigarettes a day.

Scientists from the University of California proved that social isolation and loneliness are associated with increased mortality.

Loneliness can impoverish an older person's life. On the other hand, socialisation can enrich it. Social contacts are of vital importance to keep both the body and mind healthy, especially for an older person. Without social contacts and support, older adults are prone to mental diseases such as depression. We need to remember that minds are as significant as bodies and meeting with other people is a type of therapy preventing both mental and physical diseases. In general, social contacts are one of the secrets behind successful ageing.

Did you know?

Taking part in social activities and going outside the house or apartment is critical for mental health since a lack of social contact causes feeling of loneliness and isolation.

Such feelings and fear of going outside may lead to depression. Approximately 29 % of people aged 65 and more in EU have symptoms of depression (in Poland 46%).

(Source: State of Health in the EU, 2019)

Mental health benefits of older adults socialisation

Socialisation has a wide range of mental health benefits for older adults . The main benefits are presented below, however the list below is not exhaustive; other possible benefits exist and may differ for each person.

- **Reduced level of stress.** Older adults who tend to take part in social life actively handle stress much better than those who do not. This leads to important health benefits and to an improved immune system.
- **Reduced risk of mental diseases** such as depression. Isolation and loneliness are proven factors of depression so consistent socialisation reduces the possible risk of experiencing it.
- **Less anxiety.** Similarly, older adults' socialisation reduces levels of anxiety.

More benefits of older adults socialisation

- **Cognitive health.** Positive social interactions on a regular basis keep older adults stimulated, mentally sharp and intellectually engaged. This can help prevent general cognitive decline, including memory loss, Alzheimer's disease and other forms of dementia.
- **Greater self-esteem.** Social contacts have influence on self-confidence and sense of worth.
- **More fitness.** Older adults with diverse social supports are more likely to exercise regularly, which leads to a host of physical, mental and cognitive benefits.
- **Longer lifespan.** This factor is the sum of the above mentioned benefits. Due to the reduced level of stress, anxiety and risk of mental diseases as well as greater fitness, lifespan may be longer. Moreover, there is also a higher likelihood of living longer with good physical and mental health.

<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=XaC4WUOSye4>

Keep regular routines and schedules as much as possible for eating, sleeping, and activities you enjoy.

Suggestions for further reading

If you want to find more about mobility and mental health:

[Active social life may delay memory loss](#)

[Loneliness and social isolation as risk factors for mortality](#)

[Social isolation, loneliness, and all-cause mortality in older men and women](#)

Quiz

Click the **Quiz** button to edit this object

 BUILT | **MODULE 7** | **CHAPTER 1** Mobility and mental health

Older people who lead an intense social life are happier, healthier and more likely to live longer, than older people who don't have an active social life.

- True
- False

Chapter summary

1

You have learned about the importance of mobility and connected to that socialisation in terms of older people's mental health.

2

This knowledge will help you to understand why some older adults feel isolated and lonely.

3

You may help other facilitators to understand difficulties of older adults experience, such as feeling isolated and lonely.

4

This course should have a strong influence on the perception of consequences on being socially active

5

Next chapter –'Main barriers' chapter is recommended as a continuation of this course, as well as all HEALTH modules.

Chapter completed!

Congratulations! You have successfully completed this chapter!

Summary of acquired skills

1

You know what are benefits of older adults socialisation

2

You can give some evidence on negative aspects of loneliness

3

You understand the importance of social contacts in old age

What is next?

Now you can either repeat this chapter or follow our study recommendation by clicking on one of the buttons below:

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BUILT

MODULE 7

CHAPTER 2

Main barriers

In this chapter you will find some of the most commonly reported difficulties older adults face in terms of mobility outside.

Main barriers

In order to improve the social life of older adults, it will be helpful to understand some of the obstacles older adults may encounter when trying to stay active and cultivate healthy relationships.

What will you learn in this chapter

- 1 What are the main barriers for older adults that impede mobility outside
- 2 Why older adults are not willing to participate in social activities

Main barriers for older adults in terms of mobility outside

Barriers for older adults in terms of mobility outside are unique for each person. Some key barriers are presented below, however due to the complexity of the issue the list is not exhaustive.

- Physical ailments
- Cognitive decline
- Loss of a spouse or other loved one
- Less availability of family members to assist with social activities
- Social isolation and loneliness
- Lack of a supportive community
- Lack of acceptable social opportunities
- Physical barriers in built environment

Physical ailments

Physical conditions in older age may include sensory impairments, especially hearing and vision loss, back, and neck pain, osteoarthritis, different degrees of disability, diabetes, and other chronic diseases (you can find more information about particular diseases in the HEALTHY modules). Furthermore, as people age, they are more likely to experience several conditions at the same time. Different degrees of physical disability as well as general lower physical and physiological capabilities of older people are important factors in terms of mobility.

Physical ailments

The previously mentioned physical ailments may be a barrier for some older adults and should be taken into consideration by facilitators when they try to encourage older people to lead more intensive social lives and go outside more often.

Each person needs an individual approach because physical ailments are as unique as we are. For example, someone who is using a wheelchair needs different supports than someone who has vision loss.

 Did you know?

31.7% of adults aged 65 years and older report difficulty in walking 3 city blocks when only 11.3% of adults aged 45 to 64 years have similar difficulty.

(Source:
<https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/articles/PMC3464831/>)

Cognitive decline

Cognitive decline which is also called cognitive impairment is a broad term that means some kind of problem or difficulty with one's memory, thinking, concentration, and other functions of the brain. Cognitive impairment in some cases may be a serious limitation in taking part in social activities.

Understanding how ageing changes cognition is important in terms of mobility. It can help the facilitator to understand better the changes they may notice in an older person, and whether those are out of the ordinary or not.

Cognitive decline

Being aware of the impact of cognitive decline on mobility is of the vital importance when it comes to proposing different types of social activities.

Social activities should be tailored to each person's special needs. You can find out more about cognitive decline in the HEALTH modules.

Loss of a spouse or other loved one

The loss of a spouse or other loved one is extremely hard at any age, however it may have especially devastating consequences for older people . Older adults may lose independence because sometimes couples are able to maintain their independence together by compensating for one another. For example, a husband with limited mobility may rely on his wife to help him to get up. He could be compensating for her memory loss and prompting his wife to take medications. When couples lose their spouse, they may not be able to manage their daily tasks anymore.

Loss of a spouse or other loved one

Even if both partners are in a good health, new responsibilities after the death of a spouse may be overwhelming.

Older adults who suffer from the loss of a partner can feel plunged into isolation. Meals, routines and afternoon walks may get neglected causing the surviving spouse to get caught in a continuing cycle of depression.

Less availability of family members to assist with social activities

Currently, European families tend to be smaller than in the past so reduced availability of family members to assist with social activities is quite common. Moreover, the impact of the changed family model may cause a change in the potential amount of social support given to older people. Fewer adult children may represent fewer opportunities for economic and emotional support to their older parents. Older adults, especially those who are less socially adept, may have difficulties making social contacts outside the family. This can lead to the feeling of loneliness and isolation.

Social isolation and loneliness

According to data from European Commission's Joint Research Centre, older people suffer more from social isolation than other age groups. Compared to those aged 26 to 45, adults aged 65 and over are 9 percentage points more likely not to engage often in social activities.

Social isolation and loneliness

Population ageing, the rising number of people living alone and increased use of digital technologies for communication have an influence on rising loneliness and social isolation. Social isolation significantly increases a person's risk of premature death and is associated with about a 50% percent increased risk of dementia. Poor social relationships (characterised by social isolation or loneliness) is associated with a 29% increased risk of heart disease and a 32% increased risk of stroke. Loneliness is associated with higher rates of depression, anxiety, and suicide.

Did you know?

Loneliness among heart failure patients was associated with a nearly four-fold increased risk of death, 68% increased risk of hospitalization, and 57% increased risk of emergency department visits.

(Source:
<https://www.cdc.gov/aging/publications/features/lonely-older-adults.html>)

Lack of supportive community

According to scientific data, people who live in areas with better social networks have a much higher physical mobility score than those who live in neighbourhoods with lower social capital. Thus, a lack of community support may be a significant limitation for older adults in taking part in social life even in the absence of a disability. In general, ‘caring communities’ with higher social engagement may be able to offer more assistance to older people. Older adults feel more comfortable in such communities and they are able to make social contacts more freely and frequently. The role of community support and social inclusion in outdoor mobility is of the highest importance. A support network that is close by will contribute to older adults’ feelings of safety, comfort and connectivity.

Lack of acceptable social opportunities

Lack of acceptable social opportunities is one of the most significant societal barriers to the mobility of older adults. It may be the result of stigmatisation and ageism as well as the lack of regional policy addressed to older adults. Neighbourhoods differ dramatically in terms of social opportunities for older adults.

Services which are within walking distance of home are very important. Lack of local grocery shops, local community centres or markets in the neighbourhood discourage older adults from going outside. If you want to find out more about the importance of local services, go to BUILT Modules 4 and 5.

Lack of acceptable social opportunities

However even in places with very poor supports for older people, the facilitator can take actions and, for example, create support groups, special classes for older adults and many other measures.

If you want to find more information on how to take action go to the HEALTHY modules.

Physical barriers in built environment

Poor quality or missing infrastructure such as pavements, street lighting, traffic lights or crossroads may also be a significant barrier for older people.

The most vulnerable in this case are people with limited mobility. Even if the infrastructure is of good quality, it may be not adequate for everyone's needs, for example, if there is only an underpass with a broken elevator or without an elevator. In such situations, people on wheelchairs are without an option to cross the road at a particular place. Physical barriers force older adults to change routes and sometimes this extends the journey which makes doing errands more difficult if not impossible.

Suggestions for further reading

If you want to find more about main barriers for older people:

[Mobility, disability, and social engagement in older adults](#)

[Social Isolation and Loneliness in Older Adults](#)

[Loneliness – an unequally shared burden in Europe](#)

[Loneliness and social isolation linked to serious health conditions](#)

Quiz

Click the **Quiz** button to edit this object

 BUILT **MODULE 7** **CHAPTER 2** Main barriers

Lack of community support may be a significant limitation for older adults wishing to take part in social life.

True

False

Chapter summary

1

You have learned about the main barriers for older adults that impede mobility outside.

2

This knowledge will help you to understand the main reasons why older adults don't participate in social activities.

3

You may help other facilitators to understand the difficulties experienced by older adults when going outside and create strategies to deal with them.

4

This course should have a strong influence on the perception of physiological, physical and societal barriers for older adults in terms of mobility outside the home.

5

Next chapter – 'Main needs' chapter is recommended as a continuation of this course, HEALTHY modules as a continuation of physical and mental impairments, as well as BUILT Modules 4 and 5 as a continuation of the issue of the significance of local services.

Chapter completed!

Congratulations! You have successfully completed this chapter!

Summary of acquired skills

1

You know the main barriers for older adults that impede mobility outside

2

You can give examples of physiological, physical and societal barriers for older adults in terms of mobility

3

You understand why older adults are not willing to participate in social activities

What is next?

Now you can either repeat this chapter or follow our study recommendation by clicking on one of the buttons below:

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BUILT

MODULE 7

CHAPTER 3

Main needs

The aim of this chapter is to present basic information about some of the main social needs of older adults.

Main needs

People are social creatures, so feeling that we are part of society or a community, being accepted and loved are basic needs at all ages. Meeting those needs has a profound effect on wellbeing and quality of life. Our social needs can change over our lifetime.

What will you learn in this chapter

- 1 | What are key social needs of older adults in terms of mobility outside

Main social needs of older adults

We have a diversity of social needs since we have individual and cultural priorities and differences. However, according to currently available data, the three needs mentioned below are very common among older adults:

- the need of proximity,
- the need for meaningful relationships,
- the need for reciprocity.

Quote

“Of all the experiences we need to survive and thrive, it is the experience of relating to others that is the most meaningful and important”.

Louis Cozolino

Professor of psychology at Pepperdine University

The need for proximity

As we age, our social networks often become less extensive and the frequency of contact with friends and loved ones tends to decrease. On the other hand, older adults may have higher-quality relationships within that smaller social network and be more involved in their community compared to younger adults.

Despite the size of the group of friends, older people need strong relationships and proximity of family and friends. This is closely related with their wellbeing and physical as well as mental health. In many cases family, spouse and adult children are a central source of support, however strong relationships in local community are also important.

The need for meaningful relationships

Meaningful social relationships, especially in old age are significant in terms of mobility, because they help to provide affection, as well as a sense of purpose and respect for older adults. Meaningful relationships have three key benefits: exchange of support, social engagement and sense of worth—all main aspects of healthy ageing. Research evidence shows the importance of social networks, which includes family, friends, neighbours and community members. A tight social network can be very beneficial to older adults by supporting their well-being and helping them to maintain their independence.

The need for reciprocity

The need for reciprocity is closely-related to both of the previously mentioned needs: the need for proximity and the need for meaningful relationships.

What is important for older adults is that as well as receiving they can also offer support, friendship or make a contribution to society themselves. This leads to a feeling of being important as well as sense of independence and purpose. Meeting all the social needs of older adults helps in maintaining well-being and good physical and mental condition.

Quiz

Click the **Quiz** button to edit this object

 BUILT | **MODULE 7** | **CHAPTER 3** Main needs

Older people need strong relationships and proximity of family and friends. These factors are closely related with their well-being, physical and mental health.

- True
- False

Chapter summary

1

You have learned about some key social needs of older adults in terms of mobility outside.

2

This knowledge will help you to understand how to meet the social needs of older adults in terms of mobility outside.

3

You may help other facilitators to understand the need for social relationships in the lives of older adults.

4

Next chapter – ‘Important places’ chapter is recommended as a continuation of this course and HEALTHY modules as a deepening topic of wellbeing.

Chapter completed!

Congratulations! You have successfully completed this chapter!

Summary of acquired skills

1

You know what are key social needs of older adults in terms of mobility outside

2

You understand how to meet basic social needs of older adults in terms of mobility outside

What is next?

Now you can either repeat this chapter or follow our study recommendation by clicking on one of the buttons below:

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BUILT

MODULE 7

CHAPTER 4

Important places

This chapter presents some of the common places which may be important as a regular destination for older adults.

Important places

One technique to improve the mobility of older people is to encourage them to visit places where other older adults go. More opportunities to meet peers means more possibilities to make social contacts and new friendships. Meeting more often and going outside the home more frequently should be encouraged.

What will you learn in this chapter

1 | What are the common places visited by older adults

2 | What places are important for older adults

Important places

Local shops, bakeries, coffee shops...

Local shops, bakeries, local coffee shops and other local services with familiar and friendly staff are a quite common destination for older adults. More information about such places can be found in BUILT Modules 4 and 5.

Markets

Markets are still popular among older groups of people. Not only have older adults an opportunity to make new contacts there, but also to buy fresh fruits and vegetables.

Churches

Many older adults go to church on a regular basis. Churches can be a major source of learning and recreation for older people who are active in the community. They can influence the lives of their older members in many ways.

Important places

Community centres

Community centres can offer many benefits for older people, such as classes, fitness groups, volunteering opportunities and chances to make connections with other older adults and people of any age.

Parks

Large municipal or local parks are very popular destinations for all age groups. This is a great place to socialise. Dog owners make arrangements to meet in groups at an agreed time to take their dogs for a walk. Park runs are also popular.

Local squares

Local squares, just like parks are full of people for most of the day. They may be venues for local events such as neighbourhood day or street runs which attract a lot of people from different age groups.

Important places

Libraries

Libraries, just like community centres, may be the venue for workshops, meetings with authors, local reading clubs or historical societies, so they are also significant points on the neighbourhood circuit of older adults.

General practitioner

The general practitioner is frequently visited by older adults who need direct advice on some health issues. It is a place where they spend some time and may also meet some peers.

Quiz

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 BUILT | **MODULE 7** | **CHAPTER 4** Important places

What places in your neighbourhood are important for older adults?

- Libraries
- Local squares
- Parks
- Community centres
- Bakeries
- Local shops
- Churches
- Coffee shops
- Markets

Chapter summary

1

You have learned about common places visited by older adults.

2

This knowledge will help you to facilitate older adults when going outside.

3

You may help other facilitators to understand what places are important for older adults.

4

Next chapter – ‘Important items’ chapter is recommended as a continuation of this course and also BUILT Modules 4 and 5.

Chapter completed!

Congratulations! You have successfully completed this chapter!

Summary of acquired skills

1

You know what are common places visited by older adults

2

You know what places are important for older adults

3

You can facilitate older adults in choosing destination to meet peers

What is next?

Now you can either repeat this chapter or follow our study recommendation by clicking on one of the buttons below:

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-
1. Laptop
 2. iPad
 3. Power bank
 4. Headphones
 5. Sunglasses
 6. Charge cable

BUILT

MODULE 7

CHAPTER 5

Necessary items

This chapter presents items which could be taken into consideration when making a list of necessary items.

Necessary items

Each older person should have a list of necessary items which should be carried every time he or she goes outside the home. Depending on the older people's physical and mental condition, the list will differ.

What will you learn in this chapter

- 1 Why list of necessary items is important when older adults go outside
- 2 What items are essential when older adults go outside
- 3 What items are additional when older adults go outside

The importance of the list of necessary items

It is crucial for older adults to have the list of necessary items with them in order not to forget about personal belongings. Problems with memory is typical issue for older adults. The best strategy to avoid unpleasant predicaments is to have the list of necessary items.

List of absolutely necessary items

- Personal ID
- Wallet
- Smartphone/telephone
- Card containing the telephone number to older adult's family member, close friend, caregiver or nurse
- Keys

List of necessary items depending on personal needs of older adult

- Watch
- Hearing aid
- Glasses
- Medical band
- Medicines
- Insulin pump
- Something sweet
- Dental prosthesis
- Cane
- Stabilizer/prosthesis of limbs
- Walker
- Tissues
- Card with older adult's address
- Card showing illnesses and allergies
- Sanitary pads
- Anti-bacterial gel
- Face mask
- Bottle of water
- Something sweet
- Umbrella
- Shopping list

Do the task!

Maria wants to prepare list of necessary items. Help her.

- ✓ Meet and get to know Maria. [You can find information about Maria here.](#)
- ✓ Read about Maria and find information about possible items which may be necessary for her.
- ✓ Choose items from the checklist described in the chapter according to Maria's needs.
- ✓ Check the answers and compare.

Quiz

Click the **Quiz** button to edit this object

 BUILT | **MODULE 7** | **CHAPTER 5** | Necessary Items

What necessary items should be on Maria's list?

- Glasses
- Hearing aid
- Something sweet
- Keys
- Smartphone/telephone
- Some form of personal identification
- Cane
- Wallet
- Card containing the telephone number for the older adult's family member, close friend, caregiver or nurse
- Dentures

Chapter summary

1

You have learned about the importance of the list of items which are necessary when older adults go outside.

2

This knowledge will help you to facilitate older adults in making effective strategies not to forget necessary items when going outside.

3

You may help other facilitators to create effective strategies for remembering what they should take when going outside.

4

Next chapter – ‘Mobility and dementia’ chapter is recommended as a continuation of this course.

Chapter completed!

Congratulations! You have successfully completed this chapter!

Summary of acquired skills

1

You understand the importance of the list of necessary items when older adults go outside

2

You know essential and additional items when older adults go outside

3

You know how to create effective strategies not to forget important items

What is next?

Now you can either repeat this chapter or follow our study recommendation by clicking on one of the buttons below:

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BUILT

MODULE 7

CHAPTER 6

Mobility and dementia

The aim of this chapter is to present some rules on how support people with dementia to move in their vicinity

Offering a walk

Mobility is an essential factor positively influencing our health, not only physical but also mental. It also has great importance in cognitive impairments as keeping active may help slow down the disease process.

If you plan to take a person with dementia for a walk you should try not to overwhelm her with too much walking routes choices. It is very difficult for a person with dementia to take decision. Decision between max. Two options is recommendable.

Remembering some routes

Remembering routes by a person with dementia is a great challenge for her. However, it might be very beneficial because she or he can walk alone, which is important for the feeling of dignity and independence. It is also beneficial for the carers. Quite often, a person with dementia leaves the house unspotted and may get lost if she does not know the route. Therefore, it is vital to teaching a person with dementia the primary route to move safely and get back home.

Landmarks as orientation marks

Landmarks are essential orientation marks for persons with dementia. When teaching them primary routes, we need to pay attention to vivid advertisements, benches or peculiar-looking trees. Such landmarks should stand out from the background and mark some changes in movement (turning left or right).

Progressive disclosure

It is challenging for a person with dementia to remember the information. Therefore, such a person should not be overloaded with the bulk of details, which should be gradually dropped down. When creating a well-structured path, we should think of a hierarchy of information, from the most general to more detailed. A good approach is progressive disclosure which is used f.ex. on airports, which sequences the data and causes users not to feel overwhelmed by what they encounter.

Caring community

Public spaces are designed usually by young and fit people, who do not have problems with mobility and cognitive impairments. It is therefore important to be aware of the needs of older adults also providing innovative solutions. Caring communities are consisted of facilitators who are aware of the needs of others, especially the most vulnerable groups such as older adults or children.

When designing public spaces various groups of users should be involved in order to better respond to their needs.

Inclusive symbols

Visual communication is essential for people with dementia. Quite often these persons are not capable of reading standard signs and they need signs with a clear relationship between a symbol and what it represents. They should be:

- legible
- with contrast, so that the text and signs are well visible
- with proper font and text size. Use the sentence case as it is the easiest to understand and font without serif (like i.e. Arial)

Toilet

Ticket

Stairs

Lift

Blokkie Om - dementia inclusive design example

Blokkie Om is a dementia-friendly, walkable shopping route for people in a Rotterdam neighbourhood. Two routes are marked yellow or green. The routes have additional benches, and special attention was paid to sidewalk entry and exit ramps for people that need them along the way. The project is monitoring the success of the route, and other routes in different neighbourhoods are planned.

[You can find more information here.](#)

Eugene Pauly story

Eugene Pauly was one of the most recognizable patients in the history of neurology. When Eugene was 70, he was diagnosed with virus encephalomyelitis. After the illness he was totally different person who had severe difficulties with his memory. Why is he mentioned here? Because scientific experiments with Eugene revealed the power of habit is stronger than expected. Even people with mental illnesses such as amnesia can create habits that help them survive which is greatly explained in Charles Duhigg's book "The power of habit". Awareness of that power may be helpful for people with dementia as well.

Eugene Pauly's walks

Charles Duhigg in his book "The power of habit" explains how Eugene Pauly was able to go for a walk unassisted. Experiments show that Eugene could make new habits although it was impossible for him to remember what he did few seconds ago. Guidelines such as certain trees or places or location of mailboxes were always the same. Therefore, despite that Eugene couldn't recognize his house, habits almost always guided him to his front door. However, experiments also shown that habits are very fragile. If guidelines change even slightly, habit doesn't work. Broken tree branches on the street or construction works confused Eugene and he got lost.

The story of Eugene Pauly shows key issues in dementia inclusive approach. First of all, people with mental impairments even those with advanced amnesia have ability to learn new habits. Secondly, dementia inclusive design could be helpful for them to create new habits and cope with everyday tasks. Finally, neighbourhoods designed for all have profound effect on people's independence.

Suggestion for further reading

If you want to find more about mobility and dementia:

[Dementia and the Outdoors Guidance Note](#)

Help Cornelia

Help Cornelia with finding the best way to the new supermarket. Cornelia goes for a walk to the nearest park and local shops regularly. She tried to visit new place in the neighbourhood but she got lost two times. Help Cornelia choosing the best way for her to remember. Take special attention to details.

- ✓ Meet and get to know Cornelia. [You can find information about Cornelia here.](#)
- ✓ Check carefully two photographs of the way to the supermarket.
- ✓ Try to find local landmarks and orientation points on the photographs. Even small details could be helpful.
- ✓ Take into consideration dementia inclusive design described in the paragraph.
- ✓ Decide which way is easier to remember for Cornelia.
- ✓ Check the answers and compare.

Quiz

Click the **Quiz** button to edit this object

 BUILT | **MODULE 7** | **CHAPTER 6**

What should be taken into consideration when choosing a route for a person with dementia?

- Condition of local shops
- Size of trees
- Symbols with contrast and proper font size
- Landmarks as orientation marks
- Properly designed signs

Chapter summary

1

You have learned about the importance of the dementia inclusive design.

2

This knowledge will help you to facilitate older adults in making effective strategies when remembering the routes.

3

You may help other facilitators to create effective strategies for older adults when remembering the routes.

4

Next chapter – ‘Safe routes’ chapter is recommended as a continuation of this course.

Chapter completed!

Congratulations! You have successfully completed this chapter!

Summary of acquired skills

1

You understand the importance of the dementia inclusive design

2

You know dementia inclusive design rules

3

You know how to create effective strategies when remembering the routes

What is next?

Now you can either repeat this chapter or follow our study recommendation by clicking on one of the buttons below:

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BUILT

MODULE 7

CHAPTER 7

Safe routes

The aim of this chapter is to present some rules on how to choose a safe route for older adults.

Safe routes

Walking is a popular, inexpensive, and low impact way for older people to meet physical activity guidelines and socialise. The issue of personal safety is of the highest importance in terms of mobility outside.

What will you learn in this chapter

- 1 | What are the principles of choosing a safe route
- 2 | How to assess the built environment in terms of mobility needs of older adults

Choosing a safe route

1**2****3**

Decide about the aim of the trip

Ask an older adult where he or she wants to go. Is it a local centre, church, library or the nearest grocery store. You can use a list of important places from chapter 4 to propose possible destinations.

Choosing a safe route

1

2

3

Safety first

Safety is a key issue relating to mobility outside. Each route should be chosen on the basis of safety. If it is possible, choose routes with streetlights and low road congestion. If an older person is afraid of choosing some routes, propose another one which seems safer. Try to make the older adult as comfortable as it is possible.

Choosing a safe route

1

2

3

Use sidewalks

Only choose routes with safe sidewalks. If it is possible, try to choose sidewalks without high kerbs, cracks and holes. If this is not possible, choose the route according to the older adults' physical capabilities. Avoid underpasses without elevators or special stairs if the older adult has mobility problems.

Choosing a safe route

Choose safe intersections

Try to choose intersections that allow time to cross safely. Where possible, choose roads with light traffic. If this is not possible, choose crossings that give the older person time to cross safely and comfortably.

Choosing safe route

Remember about the rest places and toilets

For longer walks, rest places and toilets can be important. Try to choose routes with benches or near places where older people can have a seat. If it is a long walk, try to choose a route that passes near public toilets.

Choosing safe route

Take necessary items

Make a list of necessary items which an older adult should always have. Make sure that the older person has items from the list. This list should be prepared according to the specific needs of the older adult.

Safe routes checklist

1Decide about the aim of the trip

2Safety first

3Use sidewalks

4Choose safe intersections

5Remember about the need for rest places
and bathrooms along the route

6Take necessary items

Help Antonio

Help Antonio with going from his apartment to a public library. Friends always borrow books for Antonio, who is a bookworm, however this week no one can do it. Antonio can go to the library only with the help of a facilitator as he is not used to going there on his own.

- ✓ Meet and get to know Antonio. [You can find information about Antonio here.](#)
- ✓ Read about Antonio and identify Antonio's barriers in terms of mobility.
- ✓ Identify Antonio's needs.
- ✓ Use Google Street View to go from place A to B. Use three possible routes.
- ✓ Follow the instructions on how to choose safe route.
- ✓ Identify physical barriers in built environment for Antonio. Take special attention to physical barriers such as high curbs or the condition of underpasses.
- ✓ Decide which route is the most convenient for Antonio.
- ✓ Check the answers and compare.

Quiz

Click the **Quiz** button to edit this object

 BUILT | **MODULE 7** | **CHAPTER 7**

What should be taken into consideration when choosing a safe route for an older adult?

- Streetlights
- The weather
- The condition of public transportation
- Pedestrian crossings
- Public toilets and places to rest
- Safety
- The duration of green light for pedestrians
- Traffic congestion
- The condition of sidewalks

Chapter summary

1

You have learned about the principles of choosing a safe route.

2

This knowledge will help you to facilitate older adults when they leave their home.

3

You may help other facilitators in assessing the built environment to enhance the mobility of older adults.

4

This course should have a strong influence on practical skills associated with assessment of the built environment to support the mobility of older adults.

Chapter completed!

Congratulations! You have successfully completed this chapter!

Summary of acquired skills

1

You know principles of choosing the safe route

2

You can assess the built environment in terms of mobility needs of older adults

3

You can choose the safe route for older adults

What is next?

Now you can either repeat this chapter or follow our study recommendation by clicking on one of the buttons below:

[Restart](#)[Next](#)

Quiz

Click the **Quiz** button to edit this object

 BUILT **MODULE 7** Mobility outside

The level of community support may be a significant factor for older adults in taking part in social life.

- True
- False

Module summary

1

You have learned about: the importance of mobility and associated socialisation to support the mental health of older adults, the main barriers for older people and their mobility needs, important places for this age group, necessary items and dementia inclusive design as well as safe routes.

2

This knowledge will help you to understand why some older adults feel isolated and lonely and how to overcome such obstacles and encourage them to actively take part in social life.

3

You may help other facilitators to understand difficulties of older adults who may feel isolated and lonely and strategies for how to deal with them.

4

You have acquired skills of identifying mobility barriers for older adults, their social needs, and choosing safe routes as well as assessing the quality of the built environment through the microscope of mobility measures.

5

This course will influence your perception of the mobility of older adults and the role of social inclusion and inclusive design in mobility.

Module completed!

Congratulations! You have successfully completed this module!

Summary of acquired skills

1

You know the importance of mobility and main needs as well as barriers for older adults according to that

2

You know strategies helpful for older adults when they go outside

3

You can identify mobility barriers in the built environment, choose safe routes and propose inclusive design

What is next?

Now you can either repeat this module or follow our study recommendation by clicking on one of the buttons below:

[Restart](#)[Next](#)[BUILT
MODULE 4](#)[BUILT
MODULE 5](#)[HEALTHY](#)